

Serbian Association for Cancer Research

**5th CONGRESS OF SDIR:
TRANSLATIONAL POTENTIAL OF
CANCER RESEARCH IN SERBIA**

**ABSTRACT
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with international participation
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President of SDIR-5 Congress
dr sc. med. Mirjana Branković-Magić

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NF- κ B inactivation is important for disulfiram suppression of fibrosarcoma which can be rescued by NF- κ B stimulator mebendazole in hamster model

Kosta J. Popović¹, Dušica, J. Popović², Dušan Lalošević², Dejan Miljković²,
Jovan K. Popović^{3*}, Ivan Čapo²

¹*Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Hajduk Veljkova 3,
 21137 Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia*

²*Department of Histology and Embriology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad,
 Hajduk Veljkova 3, 21137 Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia*

^{3*}*Department of Pharmacology, Toxicology and Clinical Pharmacology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad,
 Hajduk Veljkova 3, 21137 Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia*

Background: We investigated involvement of NF- κ B in the anticancer effect of disulfiram and metformin combination on fibrosarcoma in hamsters. **Material and Methods:** Hamsters (both sexes; ~ 70 g) were randomly allocated to control and experimental groups (8 animals per group). In all groups, 2×10^6 BHK-21/C13 cells in 1 ml were injected subcutaneously into the animals' backs. Peroral treatments were carried out with combination of NF- κ B suppressors disulfiram (50 mg/kg/day) and metformin (500 mg/kg/day) and by the combination with addition of rescue daily doses of NF- κ B stimulator mebendazole 460 mg/kg, via a gastric probe after tumor inoculation. After 19 days all animals were sacrificed. Blood samples were collected for hematological and biochemical analyses, the tumors were excised and weighed, and their diameters and volumes were measured. The tumor samples were pathohistologically and immunohistochemically assessed (Ki-67, PCNA, CD34, CD31, COX4, Cytochrome C, GLUT1, iNOS), and the main organs were toxicologically tested. **Results:** The combination of NF- κ B suppressors disulfiram and metformin significantly inhibited fibrosarcoma growth in hamsters without toxicity, compared to control. Co-treatment with NF- κ B stimulator mebendazole completely blocked anticancer activity of the NF- κ B suppressors disulfiram and metformin combination, most likely by NF- κ B stimulation. **Conclusion:** Anticancer effect of the combination of NF- κ B suppressors disulfiram and metformin may be through NF- κ B suppression and the combination may be used as an effective and safe candidate for novel nontoxic adjuvant and relapse prevention oncological therapy.

Keywords: disulfiram; metformin; mebendazole; hamsters; fibrosarcoma

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